

Supporting Information

Next-Generation Self-Powered Photodetectors using 2D Bismuth Oxide Selenide Crystals

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Figure S1. The electrochemical exfoliation process with the application of a potential.

Figure S2. Top-view scanning electron microscope (SEM) image reveals the distinctive flake-like structure of exfoliated $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$.

Figure S3. Raman spectroscopy measurements of the bulk materials, highlighting the associated peaks and their assigned vibrational modes.^{S1}

Figure S4. The current-voltage (IV) characteristics of the $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ -based PEC photodetector. (a) IV characteristics with dark and light source (b) on-off response with chop on and off light sources were obtained using a linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) approach at a scanning speed of 10 mV s^{-1} , and the system was illuminated with a 420 nm LED. Notably, the results reveal a distinct on-off response.

Figure S5. The photocurrent density characteristics of PEC photodetectors employing a few layers of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ under illumination by LEDs with wavelengths of (a) 633 nm, (b) 720 nm, and (c) 940 nm, all operated at an applied voltage of 0.5 V relative to SCE in a 1 M KOH solution. The power of the LEDs was systematically increased from 100 to 800 mW.

Table S1. A comprehensive comparison of the performance of a photodetector based on Bi₂O₂Se with previously published results.

Materials	Device configuration	Measurement conditions		Responsivity (mA W ⁻¹)	Wavelength (nm)	Reference
		Electrode	Applied Potential			
GaSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.3 V vs. RHE	160	455	23
				19.5	455	
GeSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	0.3 V vs. SCE	0.044	Simulated sunlight	31
				0.076	Simulated sunlight	
Rh-Cr ₂ O ₃ modified p-AlGa _{1-x} N nanowires.	PEC-type	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 V vs. Ag/AgCl	183	255 nm	32
lignin-derived GQDs	PEC-type	0.01 M KCl	0.6 V vs. SCE	0.003	Simulated sunlight	33
SnSe ₂ /SnSe hetero-structures	PEC-type	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	0.4 V vs. SCE	0.523	475	34
InSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.3 M KOH	0 V vs. SCE	10.14	365	35
GeSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	0.3 V vs. RHE	0.044	Simulated sunlight	36
In ₂ O ₃ microrods	PEC-type	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1 M KOH	0.6 V vs. Ag/AgCl	21.19	365	37
InSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.2 M KOH	1 V vs. SCE	3.3 × 10 ⁻³	Simulated sunlight	38
				4.9 × 10 ⁻³	Simulated sunlight	
Black phosphorous nanosheets	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	0 V vs. SCE	1.9 × 10 ⁻³	Simulated sunlight	39
				2.2 × 10 ⁻³	Simulated sunlight	
Perovskite (CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI ₃)	Metal-semiconductor-metal	0.1 M KOH	5 V	4.4	633	40
SnS	PEC-type	0.1 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.6 V	0.018	365	41
PBDTT-ffQx/PCBM bulk heterojunction	Metal-semiconductor-metal	-	10 V	1.15 × 10 ³	365	42
SnS/RGO hybrid nanosheets	FET	-	V _{DS} = 5V, V _g = 0 V	180	visible light	43
Bi₂O₂Se	PEC-type	1 M KOH	0.5 V vs. SCE	0.097	420 nm	This Work

Table S2. A comprehensive comparison of response time of a photodetector based on Bi₂O₂Se with previously published results.

Materials	Device configuration	Measurement conditions		Responsivity (mA W ⁻¹)	Response time	Reference
		Electrode	Wavelength (nm)			
Few-layers BP	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	Simulated sunlight	2.65	0.5 Sec	S2
2D Te nanosheets	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	Simulated sunlight	43×10^{-6}	54.5 ms	S3
2D Bi nanosheets	PEC-type	1 M NaOH	Simulated sunlight	0.152	0.3 sec	S4
Few-layers Bi ₂ S ₃	PEC-type	0.1 M KOH	365 nm	8.9	0.1 sec	S5
Few-layers SnS	PEC-type	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	365 nm	5.2	0.3 sec	S6
lignin-derived GQDs	PEC-type	0.01 M KCl	Simulated sunlight	0.003	1.5 sec	S7
SnSe ₂ /SnSe hetero-structures	PEC-type	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	475 nm	0.523	13 ms	S8
In ₂ O ₃ Nano cube	PEC-type	1 M KOH	365	44.43	20 ms	S9
InSe nanosheets	PEC-type	0.3 M KOH	365	10.14	2 ms	S10
Bi₂O₂Se	PEC-type	1 M KOH	420 nm	0.097	82 ms	This Work

Table S3. A comprehensive comparison of our PEC photodetector with others types of photodetectors.

Materials	Device configuration	Measurement conditions	Responsivity (A W ⁻¹)	Reference
		Applied Potential		
NiTe ₂ /WS ₂ heterostructures	FET	V _{ds} = 1 V, V _g = -40-80 V	0.3	S11
MoS ₂ nanosheets	Schottky-contact	V _{ds} = 2 V, V _g = -50 V	15	S12
BP/ MAPbI _{3-x} Cl _x	Schottky-contact	V _{ds} = -2 V, V _g = 30 V	10 ⁸	S13
Few-layer BP flakes	Schottky-contact	V _{ds} = -1 V, V _g = 10 V	3.5×10^{-3}	S14
Single-Layer MoS ₂	FET	V _{ds} = 1 V, V _g = 0 V	420×10^{-6}	S15
Vertically Aligned SnS ₂ and RGO	<i>p-n</i> junction	V _{ds} = 2 V, V _g = 5 V	1.3	S16
Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x MXene/Si	Schottky-contact	V _{ds} = -2 V, V _g = 0 V	0.3	S17
Layered InSe	FET	V _{ds} = 1 V, V _g = 0 V	27	S18
SnS ₂	Metal-semiconductor-metal	V _{ds} = 10 V, V _g = 0 V	2	S19
Bi ₂ O ₂ Se	PEC-type	0.5 V vs. SCE	97×10^{-6}	This Work

External Quantum Efficiency (EQE, η)

External quantum efficiency (η) is defined as the ratio of electron-hole pairs generated to the number of incident photons. The equation for calculating the quantum efficiency is shown below: ^{S20}

$$\text{EQE} = \eta = \frac{hcR}{q\lambda} \quad \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation S1}$$

where:

- λ is the wavelength of the incident light,
- c is speed of light,
- R is the responsivity of the device,
- h is Planck's constant,
- q is the elementary charge.

The calculated η is plotted in Figure S as a function of different wavelengths.

Figure S6. External quantum efficiency (EQE) of the devices with different wavelength.

Figure S7. The photocurrent density characteristics of PEC photodetectors employing a few layers of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ under illumination by LEDs with wavelengths of (a) 420 nm, (b) 460 nm, and (c) 533 nm, all operated at an applied voltage of 0.5 V relative to SCE in a 1 M Na_2SO_4 solution. The power of the LEDs was systematically increased from 100 to 800 mW.

Figure S8. Depicts the power-dependent (a) Responsivity and (b) The specific detectivity of PEC-type $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ -based photodetectors in a 1 M Na_2SO_4 solution, showcasing their performance across five distinct illumination wavelengths.

Figure S9. The photocurrent density characteristics of PEC photodetectors under two distinct light illuminations: (a) 420 nm and (b) 460 nm. These photodetectors were operated at an applied voltage of 0 V relative to SCE while varying the power.

Hall measurements

In order to confirm the polarity of the $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ we further conducted Hall measurements using DX-100 Hall effect system in Van der Pauw geometry on bulk crystals in room temperature. Rectangular shaped crystal was chosen and silver paste was deposited on the corners of the sample as a contact electrode, the thickness of the sample was measured as 2 mm. In the measurement magnetic field was swept from -500 mT to +500 mT and current was applied 1mA, and every time the Hall voltage and Hall coefficient found to be negative which signifies that $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ has n type polarity. The bulk carrier concentration was calculated as $4.09 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Thickness d (cm)	Magnetic Field (mT)	Temperature (K)	Current (mA)	Hall Voltage (mV)	Hall coefficient (cm^3/C)	Bulk carrier concentration ($1/\text{cm}^3$)
0.2	500	300.05	1	-3.822981	-15291.92	4.09E+14

Figure S10. The electrochemical stability of exfoliated $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{Se}$ in a 1 M KOH solution. (b) A linear sweep voltammetry analysis of the on/off photocurrent response under a 0.5 V bias (vs. SCE) while subjecting the sample to 500 mW illumination from a 420 nm LED. Subsequently, (a) and (c) provide enlarged on/off cycles extracted from the data in Figure (b), showcasing the photocurrent responses during the initial and final portions of the measurement.

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